

RESEARCH ARTICLE

OPEN ACCESS

Received: 24-07-2024

Accepted: 27-09-2024

Published: 14-10-2024

Citation: Hemalatha KS, Srikanth C, Madhavi K, Sriprakash G (2024) Effect of Morphology and Concentration of CeO₂ Nanoceria on the Thermal Stability of Polyvinyl Alcohol Films. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 17(39): 4058-4065. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17i39.2380>

* **Corresponding author.**chivukulasrik@gmail.com**Funding:** None**Competing Interests:** None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Effect of Morphology and Concentration of CeO₂ Nanoceria on the Thermal Stability of Polyvinyl Alcohol Films

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the thermal stability of polyvinyl alcohol films under different concentrations of CeO₂ nanoceria. **Method:** Cerium Oxide doped polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) nano-composites were synthesized by the traditional solution casting method for various concentrations of nano CeO₂ by solution combustion method. The thermal properties of prepared PVA-2.5 wt% CeO₂, PVA-7.5 wt% CeO₂, PVA-12.5 wt% CeO₂, and PVA-25 wt% CeO₂ composite films were elucidated by using techniques such as Differential Scanning Calorimetry, Thermogravimetry analysis and Differential Thermal analysis. **Findings:** The glass transition temperature of the pure PVA is found to be 114°C, whereas it varies between 110°C-120°C for composite films. The melting temperature of the composite films is the same as that of pure PVA except in the case of 7.5wt% CeO₂ and 25wt% CeO₂ composites. The reduced melting point of these composites elicits a decrease in crystallinity. A 12.5 wt % and 25 wt% CeO₂-PVA nano-composite films exhibit an increase in the final degradation temperature, a high specific heat capacity, low mass loss, and a larger residual weight, indicating their potential applicability in thermal coating and thermal sensing applications. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) films are being used routinely as a dielectric layer for electrical applications due to the good physiochemical and dialectic properties of the material. An incorporation of CeO₂ nanoceria improves not only the thermal but also the mechanical properties of PVA and extends its application for electrical and optical operation. Here in the present study, different concentrations of CeO₂ were incorporated with the PVA and analysed for the thermal properties. The study showed that 12.5 wt % and 25 wt% CeO₂-PVA nano-composite enhanced PVA film thermal stability.

Keywords: PVA-CeO₂ Nanocomposites; Differential Scanning Calorimetry; Thermogravimetry Analysis and Differential Thermal Analysis; Physical properties and thermal properties

1 Introduction

One of the most important characteristics of polyvinyl alcohol; PVA-CeO₂ nanocomposite polymer materials is their temperature stability. The thermal stability of PVA-CeO₂ nano composite remains associated with the materials' mechanical qualities, toughness, spectral stability, shelf lives, and life cycles. Excellent characteristics of nano CeO₂ particles are their capacity to absorb ultraviolet light and their sensitivity to gases.⁽¹⁻³⁾ Effective CeO₂-organic polymer UV-resistant composite materials and gas sensors can also be created by combining them with organic polymers. Previous research investigations have reported that the incorporation of metals and blended into nanoparticles with PVA provides an extended thermal stability of the material.⁽⁴⁻⁶⁾ Further, crossed-linked PVA attains higher insulation properties along with mechanical properties. Among the inorganic nanoparticles to be included in the polymer, rare earth salts and rare earth oxides have shown a considerable effect on the structural, optical, and thermal properties.^(7,8) Cerium oxide (CeO₂) was selected for this investigation because of its abundance among rare earth elements, good transmittance in the visible spectrum, high refractive index in the visible area, good thermal and chemical stability, and inexpensive cost⁽⁹⁾. It has also shown potential applications in fuel and solar cells, catalysts, oxygen and NO₂ sensors, polishing agents, gate oxides, optical devices, and coating materials⁽¹⁰⁾.

A composition-dependent study of PVA-CeO₂ nanocomposite films⁽¹¹⁾ has revealed that the 2.5 wt% CeO₂ film has good photoluminescence, nearly equal to that of CeO₂ itself. Since CeO₂ has good thermal stability, it was felt that the addition of CeO₂ nanoparticles to PVA may improve the stability of the polymer. The cross-linking also changes the dielectric properties of PVA along with stiffness. Undoubtedly PVA is a useful material for various electric and optical design and operations but associated with several properties. In order to extend the application of PVA it is essential to have mechanical and thermal properties that can be incorporated via CeO₂ nanocerium. In previous studies, it has been shown that the PVA conjugated with nanoparticles improves material thermal and mechanical properties. The analytical profiling of the concentration of CeO₂ that can improve the thermal properties of PVA is yet to be optimized. The key question remains unexplained i.e. how do CeO₂ nanocerium change the thermal properties of PVA? Further, the concentration of CeO₂ nanocerium required for the ideal thermal properties needs to be examined. In the present study, emphasis was given to addressing the morphology and concentration of CeO₂ nanocerium on the thermal properties of PVA.

2 Methodology

Poly Vinyl Alcohol (PVA) having an average molecular weight of 125,000 and 98% hydrolysis was obtained from Aldrich, India, and Cerium nitrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O) and Citric acid (C₆H₈O₇) was purchased from CDH Ltd., India. CeO₂ nanoparticles were prepared by solution combustion method and the nanocomposite films were prepared by solvent casting method. Details of the thick films and their preparation are reported earlier⁽¹²⁾. DSC studies were carried out using Mettler Toledo DSC 822e in the temperature range 30°C to 240°C at a heating rate of 10°C/minute in the nitrogen atmosphere for all the nanocomposite films while from -10°C to 240°C in the case of PVA to understand the thermal transition behavior of the prepared samples. TG and DTA measurements were carried out using a Perkin Elmer, Diamond TG/DTA analysis apparatus in the temperature range 50°C to 75°C in the nitrogen atmosphere with a flow rate of 100ml per minute and a heating rate of 10°C per minute. In the study, the temperature range, variation of heat flow residual weight, and derivative weight were

determined for all five samples i.e. PVA, PVA-2.5 wt. % CeO₂, PVA-7.5 wt. % CeO₂, PVA-12.5 wt. % CeO₂ and PVA-25 wt. % CeO₂.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Influence of CeO₂ nanoparticles on glass transition and melting temperatures of PVA: using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Figure 1 shows the variation of T_g (glass transition temperature) and T_m (melting temperature) of PVA and PVA-CeO₂ nano-composite films as obtained from DSC thermograms. A dehydration temperature (a small dip at 36°C), glass transition temperature (a broad peak at 114°C), and melting temperature (a sharp endothermic peak at 223°C) found in Pure PVA are in good agreement with the literature⁽¹³⁾. All the nano-composite films also exhibit identical behavior. The decrease in melting temperature is seen in 7.5 wt% and 25 wt% composite films, whereas the other concentrations of composite films exhibit almost the same values. The decrease in melting temperature indicates the decrease in crystallinity in these composite films. The shift in T_g values of polymer nano-composite films in comparison with pure PVA, indicates the impact of filler ceria on the polymer and also points to the interaction between the polymer and the nano ceria. At this temperature, the composite films change from a solid glassy state to a rubbery state. The weak endothermic peak in all the films represents the dismissal of physically adsorbed water. The DSC study also facilitates the estimation of the specific heat capacity of the samples (Figure 2) by comparing the heat flow rate of a blank and a sample in a particular temperature range. The details of the procedure are reported earlier⁽¹⁴⁾ and the same procedure is applied in this present study and the results are tabulated in Table 1. The specific heat capacity is found to be increasing for all the composite films compared to pure PVA and the highest value is observed in 25wt% CeO₂ nano-composite films. The higher value of specific heat capacity indicates the higher thermal stability of the composite films, wherein 25wt% CeO₂ shows the maximum.

Fig 1. Figure demonstrates DSC thermogram of PVA and nanocomposite films

Table 1. Specific heat capacity (C_p) of pure PVA and PVA-CeO₂ nano-composite films

Sample	C_p (cal g ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹)
PVA	0.36
PVA-2.5wt% CeO ₂	0.66
PVA-7.5wt% CeO ₂	0.59
PVA-12.5wt% CeO ₂	0.79
PVA-25wt% CeO ₂	0.86

Fig 2. Variation of heat flow versus time of (a) Pure PVA (b) 2.5 wt% CeO₂ (c) 7.5 wt% CeO₂ (d) 12.5 wt % CeO₂ and (e) 25 wt% CeO₂ composite films with reference to (f) blank

3.2 Morphological and nano CeO₂ effect on the thermal stability of PVA: using Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The experimental results of TGA in PVA and PVA-CeO₂ nanocomposite films showed four steps in weight loss as seen in Figure 3 and Table 2. The behavior of pure PVA subjected to different temperature ranges is discussed in detail and reported in our earlier study⁽¹⁴⁾. The results in the case of pure PVA in this study are nearly similar to our earlier reported work with negligible deviation in values which is attributed to slight changes in the thickness of the films⁽¹⁵⁾. The composites show similar behavior with lower weight loss in comparison with pure PVA indicating their higher thermal stability.

Fig 3. Residual weight (%) versus temperature of pure PVA and composite films

The final residual weight of pure PVA is just 0.01% indicating a complete decrease in thermal stability of the polymer in this temperature range (around 645°C). In the case of PVA-CeO₂ composites, a 10 to 15% reduction in weight loss in the first decomposition stage indicates an increase in thermal stability during this stage. The next two decomposition stages also show a decrease in weight loss in the composite films compared to pure PVA. In the final decomposition stage, a larger residual mass was observed in all the composite films compared to pure PVA at 645°C.

Table 2. Data obtained by Thermogravimetry (TG) for pure PVA and PVA-CeO₂ composite films

Sample	Temperature range (°C)		% Weight loss	
			Partial	Stage I & II
PVA	I stage	80-230	8.07	80.43
	II stage	230-332	72.36	
	III stage	332-487	15.18	
	IV stage	487-645	3.88	
PVA-2.5wt% CeO ₂	I stage	95-235	8.12	77.82
	II stage	235-335	69.70	
	III stage	335-495	13.98	
	IV stage	495-645	3.61	
PVA-7.5wt% CeO ₂	I stage	75-230	9.44	80.14
	II stage	230-330	70.70	
	III stage	330-485	15.49	
	IV stage	485-645	3.22	
PVA-12.5wt% CeO ₂	I stage	80-218	7.49	71.31
	II stage	218-320	63.82	
	III stage	320-475	17.58	
	IV stage	475-645	5.56	
PVA-25wt% CeO ₂	I stage	85-216	5.87	60.55
	II stage	216-331	54.68	
	III stage	331-465	13.35	
	IV stage	465-645	4.57	

It is clear from Table 2 that the weight loss at each stage is reduced almost monotonically with an increase in CeO₂. Reducing trends in weight loss at each stage and increasing residual weight in the composites indicate the enhanced thermal stability of the composites. The final residual weight in PVA is 0.01% while it is 21%, in the PVA-25 wt% CeO₂ composite film. The 25 wt% CeO₂ film has the highest thermal stability among all the composites. The surface morphology and filler distribution are studied using a Scanning Electron microscope and the results were reported. The micrographs reveal that the nano-ceria particles are uniformly distributed throughout the PVA matrix. For higher concentrations of nanoparticles (12.5 wt% CeO₂ and 25 wt% CeO₂) of the composites, there is an aggregation of CeO₂ particles. With the increase of filler content, the aggregation of ceramic particles increases, which in turn increases the porosity of the composite. For higher concentrations of the composites, the connectivity among the ceramic particles increases which improves the thermal properties. Thus, the network of the individual particles is the key factor in controlling the electrical, mechanical, and thermal properties⁽¹⁵⁾. The chain mobility which is dictated by the molecular weight of the filler determines the final physical property of the polymer.

In the present study, the improvement in the thermal stability of the composites can be attributed to lower mobility of the polymer chains which is due to higher molecular weight caused by the inclusion of filler particles⁽¹⁶⁾. The SEM characterization of the composite films with 25wt% CeO₂ has revealed a marked difference in morphology, looking like the precursor to nanoribbons corroborates their highest thermal stability. The effect of morphology and filler concentration is very much apparent through this TG behavior of the composite. It is evident from the first derivative of the TGA curves shown in Figure 4, that the temperature at which the maximum decrease of mass occurs is shifting towards the lower side with an increasing concentration of CeO₂ in PVA. The presence of three peaks shows that the side chains of PVA decompose earlier than the main chain and the main endothermic peak arises from the side-chain scission. The decrease in the weight loss with the addition of CeO₂ may be due to the cross-linking of CeO₂ and polyvinyl alcohol matrix leading to stronger intermolecular bonding.⁽¹⁷⁾ Effect of nano CeO₂ on the phase transition and thermal stability of PVA: using Differential thermal analysis (DTA).

Fig 4. Derivative weight thermogram of PVA and nanocomposite films

Fig 5. Representative DTA thermogram of PVA-25wt% CeO₂ nanocomposite films

The DTA thermogram of the PVA-25 wt% CeO₂ sample is shown in Figure 5 and is representative of the whole series. Three endothermic events and a major exothermic one is observed here and this is characteristic of the DTA curves of all the samples. The data of all the samples are tabulated in Table 3. The first endothermic peak observed in all the samples around 115°C, arises from the removal of physically adsorbed water and the thermal phase transition of the polymer matrix from a glassy to rubbery state. This occurs at progressively lower temperatures in the composites. The second weak endothermic peak at 223°C corresponds to the melting of PVA and occurs around the same temperature in all the samples. The phase transition and melting temperature obtained by DTA are in good agreement with the values recorded from DSC. The third endothermic peak marks the beginning of the decomposition process associated with the side-chain scission of C-O of PVA which was also apparent in the TG analysis. The temperature at which the third endothermic peak exists is decreased with the incorporation of filler concentration up to 7.5wt% and remains constant for further filling. The large exothermic peak at 369°C in PVA indicates the beginning of degradation of the polymer. This temperature which indicates the onset of the degradation process is shifted to the higher side in the composite films. The increase in the degradation temperature of the composite films with concentration indicates their higher thermal stability. Amongst all the composite films, maximum thermal stability is achieved in 25wt% CeO₂-PVA film.

Table 3. Glass transition temperature (T_g), melting temperature (T_m), decomposition temperature (T_{d1}), and completer degradation temperature (T_{d2}) of pure PVA and PVA-CeO₂ nanocomposites obtained by differential thermal analysis

Sample	First endothermic peak (T_g -° C)	Second endothermic peak (T_m -° C)	Third endothermic peak (T_{d1} -° C)	Fourth exothermic peak (T_{d2} -° C)
PVA	115	223	276	369
PVA-2.5wt% CeO ₂	119	224	275	366
PVA-7.5wt% CeO ₂	115	222	265	384
PVA-12.5wt% CeO ₂	123	218	263	391
PVA-25wt% CeO ₂	124	219	265	379

It is known that polymers have dual functions, including reducing and capping agents for nanoparticles (NPs) encompassing, which provide chemical and environmental stability. It is reported that modifications of the chemical, mechanical, optical, and electrical properties of many polymer matrices can be accomplished by NPs incorporation. Herein, poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) is a water-soluble polymeric material that has interesting optical properties⁽¹⁸⁾. It exhibits good thermal and chemical stability, relatively high dielectric strength, is hydrophilic and nontoxic, and has sufficient storage capacity and dopants (DPs)-dependent optical and electrical properties. It is of great importance to improve several properties in terms of structure, electrical, and chemical properties. The incorporation of CeO₂ materials into the PVA matrix may change the PVA structure that will be suitable for a particular application⁽¹⁴⁾. It was formerly reported that the alteration in PVA structure with better performance could be completed via the inclusion of proper CeO₂ nanoceria into polymer chains. DSC data reveal that the T_m value increases with an increase in the concentration of the alum in the polymer film.⁽¹⁹⁾ TGA data showed the prepared polymer film is thermally stable at elevated temperatures.

4 Conclusions

Using a variety of methods, including DSC, TGA, and DTA, the thermal transition behavior and thermal stability of PVA and PVA-CeO₂ nanocomposite films were investigated. Because these samples have less crystallinity, several of the composites had lower melting points, which suggests that the PVA matrix and filler CeO₂ are interacting. The glass transition temperature rises to 12.5 weight percent CeO₂ concentration and then falls to 25 weight percent CeO₂ concentration. It is discovered that the specific heat capacity of all the composite films is more than that of pure PVA, reaching a maximum of 25 weight percent, indicating that this composite has the highest thermal stability. It is discovered that the melting and glass transition temperatures discovered by DSC and DTA fall into the same range. The enhancement in the final degradation temperature and the final residual mass was found to be more in nanocomposite films compared to pure PVA which reveals the improved thermal stability of nanocomposite films. The morphological and concentration effect of filler particles on the improvisation of thermal stability of polymer is seen in this study. The maximum thermal stability has been observed in the higher filler concentration of 12.5 wt% and 25 wt % CeO₂ composite films from the point of phase transition and larger residual product respectively.

The improved thermal stability of these samples (listed in Table 3) promises its use for thermal coatings and thermal sensor applications.

Acknowledgments:

Author, K.S Hemalatha, acknowledges the University Grants Commission (UGC), Government of India, and Department of Collegiate Education (DCE), Government of Karnataka, India, for the award of UGC-FIP fellowship (FIP/12th Plan/KABA027 TF-01 dated 05-06-13).

Author contribution:

KSH and CS conceptualized the study, KSH, CS, and MK carried out experiments and collected data, KSH and SG interpreted results, and CS and SG wrote the manuscript and reviewed it.

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